

CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF MODERN COMPETENCES IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: The relevance of the article, an important factor of the social order in education is the training of a competitive specialist in the labor market, which sets new requirements for the training of a modern teacher in the field of physical education and sports. Many authors in their works discuss the topic of forming the readiness of future physical education teachers to organize competitive activities of students, justifying and searching for new forms and methods of correcting the positive results of training future specialists in the field of physical education together with leading experts in this field. they insist that they need to learn more.

Key words: competence, information technology, modern system, education, qualification.

Introduction.

In recent years, we can see that research in the field of training future personnel in the field of physical education and sports has reached a new level. A number of well-known scientists deal with the issues of professional training of future physical education teachers. The problem of preparing future physical education teachers for competitive activities was revealed in the scientific research of O. L. Shabalina [3]. The general aspects of the professional training of future teachers have been considered by many scientists, therefore the structure of pedagogical activity was studied by V.N. Kuzmina [4], G.U. Matushansky was interested in the professional activity of teachers [5]. At the same time, existing studies, as well as the analysis of scientific sources devoted to the problems of preparing future physical education teachers to organize competitive activities of students, do not fully explain its impact on improving the quality of professional training of students at the university.

In practice, physical education teachers face difficulties in organizing competitive activities of students. This is one of the reasons for insufficient theoretical and practical training of graduates of pedagogical universities, which determines the urgency of searching for ways to modernize the training of future physical education teachers to organize competitive activities of students. This requires the expansion of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for students of the faculty of physical education, sports and tourism.

In the modern education system, the indispensable quality of a teacher should be his professional competence, that is, he should have "knowledge and authority in one or another field of his activity." In the psychological dictionary, professional pedagogical competence is defined as "having the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications as a carrier of certain values and ideals, which determine the teacher's pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication and the formation of the teacher's personality." is rified.

In accordance with modern trends in education, pedagogical competencies include:

- independent study;
- improve your skills or completely retrain;
- rapid assessment of the situation and their capabilities;
- making decisions and taking responsibility for them;
- adapting to changing living and working conditions;
- Develop new ways of working or modify old ones to optimize them.

According to experts, the first steps in the formation of competencies are "life skills" (*personal problems, coping with stress; time management; understanding instructions, following rules; documenting, processing and organizing text and digital information*); writing and speaking texts; implementation of business relations; being active, offering a non-standard solution, being able to intelligently defend one's point of view) and teaching one's subject.

The tasks of the educational process were solved at the interpersonal level, in the process of close communication: student - student, student - team, student - teacher.

V.A. Sukhomlinsky believed that the essence of education is communication, dialogue, communication with the child:

- teacher and student should be on equal terms, there are no priorities, communication is on an equal basis;
- communication with the student should be based on knowing his main mental core, conscious mental preferences;
- in the process of communication, the teacher should learn and strengthen the student's personal qualities, and then teach him to self-evaluate;
- the student and the teacher should always be sincere in their feelings.

The formation of these competencies is carried out at the theoretical level, but most of them are formed in practice.

The problem of improving the training of personnel for schools is related to the economic and socio-cultural changes in the society of Uzbekistan. At the current stage of Uzbekistan's development, education, inextricably linked with science, is becoming an increasingly powerful driving force for economic growth, increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of the national economy.

Access to competency-based education includes a series of consistent actions by all subjects of the educational process, and first of all, teachers. What methods and technologies should a modern teacher acquire in order for students to take responsibility, participate in joint decision-making, be able to use experience, have a critical attitude to natural and social phenomena, that is, to implement basic competencies? What professional and pedagogical competencies should the teacher have to ensure his professional growth and development? Under what conditions do competencies pass to the level of professional competence? The problem of determining professional competence and its interrelationship with the concept of competence has recently become a topic of discussion in the scientific pedagogical environment and among practicing teachers. Let's try to understand this issue.

In the most general sense, "competence" means the ability to comply with requirements, established criteria and standards, to have the necessary active knowledge, to confidently achieve results and master the situation in the relevant fields of activity and in solving a certain type of task. The concept of "competency" was used for the first time in the 60s in the USA in the context of active education, the purpose of which was to prepare specialists who can successfully compete in the labor market.

Thus, competence can be considered as a personal category; competencies as the "anatomy" of competence. From the point of view of the modern approach to the organization of labor activities, a qualified specialist (including a teacher) should be distinguished by critical thinking, that is, the ability to choose the most optimal among various solutions, the ability to work with them, information, a block of forecasting and analytical skills to successfully solve professional problems "here and now".

Let's look at several definitions of the concept of professional competence of a teacher (several definitions are placed on the display board, the teacher reads them without any evaluation).

Competence - knowledge, abilities, skills, as well as methods and methods of their implementation in activities, communication, personal development (self-development).

The work of a teacher whose pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication is carried out at a sufficiently high level, the personality of the teacher is realized, and good results are achieved in education and upbringing of schoolchildren is considered qualified. At the same time, the teacher's qualification is determined by the ratio of his professional knowledge and skills, on the one hand, and his professional positions and psychological qualities, on the other hand. (A.K. Markova)

Competence is the ability of an employee to perform his tasks with quality and accuracy under normal and extreme conditions, to successfully learn new things and to quickly adapt to changing conditions. (Vesnina V.R.)

Competence is a complex formation that includes a set of knowledge, skills, characteristics and qualities of a person, which ensures variability, optimality and efficiency in the construction of the educational process. (Adolf V.A.)

Competence is a combination of professional and pedagogical competencies. (Solovova E.N.) Noting above that competence is a specific "anatomy" of competence, it makes sense to additionally consider the issue of the essence of competence. The following professional and pedagogical competencies are distinguished:

Social-psychological competence is related to the desire to solve professional problems, including in the development mode. Professional and communicative competence that determines the level of success of pedagogical communication and interaction with subjects of the educational process. General pedagogical professional competence, which includes psychological and pedagogical preparation for the application of individual characteristics of the psychology and psychophysiology of cognitive processes of a person; to know the basics of pedagogy.

Scientific competence in the field of science:

- knowledge in the field of the taught subject, its teaching methodology.
- management competence, i.e. having the skills to conduct pedagogical analysis, set goals, plan and organize activities.
- Reflective competence, that is, the ability to see the process and result of one's pedagogical activity.
- Information and communication competence related to the ability to work in the field of IR technologies.
- competence in the field of innovation, which characterizes the teacher as an experimenter.

- creative competence, that is, the teacher's ability to bring the activity to a creative, research level.

Currently, there are various diagnostic methods that are used to some extent to solve the most urgent problem of evaluating the teacher's professional skills and the level of his professional skills. On the one hand, teachers cannot be motivated by the "knowledge-skill-skill" formula, there is no tool that can measure all the nobility of a teacher's heart, unique moments of his creativity in the process of repeated education and training. Nothing is measured by the work and perception of the teacher, they do not appear out of nowhere, but are prepared by all the previous experience of the teacher, endless communication with himself.

On the other hand, the work of a teacher collects a "success file" that reflects "all the joyful, interesting and worthwhile things that happen in the life of a teacher."

The changes taking place in the modern education system create the need to increase the teacher's qualifications and professional skills, that is, his professional competence. The main goal of modern education is to meet the current and future needs of the individual, society and the state, to become a citizen of his country who is capable of social adaptation in society, starting work, self-education and self-education. is to prepare a faceted personality. - improvement. A teacher who thinks freely, predicts the results of his activity and models the learning process is a guarantee of achieving the goals. It is for this reason that in the modern, rapidly changing world, the demand for a competent, creatively thinking, competitive person capable of educating a person has increased sharply.

Based on modern requirements, it is possible to determine the main ways of developing the professional competence of the teacher:

- work in methodological associations, creative groups;
- research activities;
- innovative activity, development of new pedagogical technologies;
- various forms of pedagogical support;
- active participation in pedagogical competitions and festivals;
- translating one's pedagogical experience;
- Use of ICT and others.

But none of the listed methods will be effective if the teacher himself does not realize the need to improve his professional skills. Hence the need to create motivation and favorable conditions for pedagogical growth. It is necessary to create conditions in which the teacher independently realizes the need to improve the level of his professional qualities. Analyzing one's pedagogical experience activates the teacher's professional self-development, as a result of which research skills are formed, which are then combined with pedagogical activity. The teacher should participate in the process of managing the school's development, which will help to improve his professional skills.

Development of professional competence is a dynamic process of assimilation and modernization of professional experience, which leads to the development of individual professional qualities, accumulation of professional experience, including continuous development and self-improvement.

The stages of formation of professional competence can be distinguished:

- introspection and awareness of need;
- self-development planning (goals, tasks, solutions);

- self-expression, analysis, self-correction.

The formation of professional competence is a cyclical process, because in the process of pedagogical activity, it is necessary to constantly improve professional skills, and each time the listed stages are repeated, but on a new scale. In general, the process of self-development is biologically determined and is related to the socialization and individuation of a person who consciously organizes his life, thus his own development. The process of formation of professional competence is also strongly dependent on the environment, so it is the environment that should stimulate professional self-development. The school should have a democratic management system. This is a staff incentive system and various forms of pedagogical monitoring (not control!), including questionnaires, tests, interviews, experience sharing, contests, and in-school events to present one's achievements. These forms of stimulation reduce the level of emotional anxiety of the teacher, affect the formation of a beneficial psychological environment in the team.

References:

1. Матвеев Л.П. Физкультурное образование: проблемы и перспективы развития / Л.П. Матвеев. - М., 1996. - 38 с.
2. Холодов Ж.К. Теория и методика физического воспитания и спорта: учебное пособие для студентов высшего учебного заведения / Ж.К. Холодов, В.С. Кузнецов. - М.: Академия. - 2000. - 480 с.
3. Шабалина О.Л. Общая педагогическая подготовка учителя физической культуры: монография / О.Л. Шабалина. - М., 2002. - 118 с.
4. Кузьмина Н.В. Методы исследования педагогической деятельности / Н.В. Кузьмина; Ленингр. гос. ун-т им. А.А. Жданова. - Ленинград. - 1970. - 114 с.
5. Матушанский Г.У. Методологические принципы компетентного подхода в профессиональном образовании / Г.У. Матушанский, О.Р. Кудаков // Казанский педагогический журнал. - 2009. - № 3. - С. 11-12.
6. Аксарина И.Ю. Профессиональная подготовленность специалиста по физической культуре и спорту / И.Ю. Аксарина // Вестник ЮГУ. - 2017. - № 1-1(44). - С. 37-42.
7. Ильин Е.П. Психология физического воспитания: учебное пособие / Е.П. Ильин. - СПб. - 2000. - 486 с.
8. Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). Boshlang'ich ta'limda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. *Молодые ученые*, 1(13), 32-37.
9. Эгамберган, Х. М. (2023). Ўқувчиларда танқидий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг педагогик ва методик асослари. *Zamonaviy fan, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish muammolarining innovatsion echimlari*, 4, 56-59.
10. Madraximovich, X. E., & Urazboyevna, U. N. (2023). O'quvchilar mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda sinfdan tashqari ustoz-shogird munosabatlarining ahamiyati. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 12), 564-566.
11. Худайназаров, Э., & Куделько, Т. А. (2023). Интерактивные задания на английском языке для студентов с использованием футбольных метафор. *Образование в сложном нестабильном мире*, 83.

12.Худайназаров, Э. Д., & Куделько, Т. А. (2022). Школа будущего (по материалам опроса школьников России и Туркменистана). In Актуальные проблемы изучения иностранных языков и литератур (pp. 158-163).

13.Davronovich, B. M. (2021). Practical work in primary mathematics education as a methodological basis for the study of mathematics. Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research, 10(6), 173-176.

14.Madraximovich, K. E. (2020). Improving the methodological training of primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(7).

15.Худойназаров, Э. М., & Бобожонов, А. Б. Синфдан ташқари ишларда ўқувчиларида мантиқий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг иновацион жиҳатлари.

16.Худойназаров, Э. М., Эсонов, Н. А., & Кучкаров, М. У. Преимущества альтернативных методов обучения.

